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Abstract Book

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Management of environment in the hospital area – importance of noise monitoring

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Context

The World Health Organization underlines the importance of noise as a negative environmental factor in the 21st Century, especially auditory and extra auditive health impact. Public health professionals recognise environmental noise as the factor leading to anxiety, hearing impairments, sleep disturbance, cognitive disorders in children and cardiovascular diseases. Environmental noise is, also, a stressogenic factor that affects human mental health. Noise monitoring, i.e. noise level control, is high priority activity in eliminating this potentially negative physical environmental factor. Noise monitoring is important for quality management in healthcare facilities, in order to achieve the greatest possible content among patients and employees.

Methods

It is possible to perform 24-hour noise measurements in order to determine the basic noise indicators (L_{day} , $L_{evening}$, L_{night} , L_{den}). We can also perform the short-term measurements in specific time terms in order to determine the equivalent/relevant noise levels, and all this in accordance to the national norms and standards SRPS ISO 1996-1 and SRPS ISO 1996-2.

Results

Research of the Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina (IPHV) shows that in Novi Sad, the percentage of highly annoyed population is 11-25% during the day, and 6-13% at night. In the vicinity of the Clinical Center of Vojvodina there is a Sports Center, a noise measuring site, referred to by the City Noise Measurement Programme as belonging to "Resting and recreation areas, hospital and rehabilitation zones, cultural and historical sites, major parks". Based on the data of IPHV for the time period 2012-2016 in SC, L_{day} was in the range 55.8 dB - 65.4 dB; $L_{evening}$ 58.5 dB - 68.6 dB; L_{night} 49.3 dB - 65.2 dB and L_{den} 59.3 dB - 71.0 dB. In relation to the national norm, basic noise indicators are overpassed in 100% of measurements, while 18% of population living nearby is highly annoyed during the day, also 10% during the night, consequently.

Discussion and conclusion

The research shows that the environmental noise originating from road traffic annoys people, but there is no exact data about connection of the most vulnerable population (hospitalised patients) to noise exposure. There is a need to determine the actual noise levels which affect the hospitalised patients through measuring the noise level, both in direct hospital environment and its nearby area, allowing a better understanding of the impact of noise in occurrence/exacerbation of the disease. Noise monitoring should be the part of the total monitoring of hospital conditions. It is important for achieving a higher level of content among patients and employees with the aim of sustainability of quality of service and environmental conditions in healthcare facilities.

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